

Perceived Influence of Educational Media on Academic Performance among Secondary School Teachers and Students in Oyo East Local Government Area, Oyo State

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Abstract

This study assessed the educational media on academic performance among secondary school students. A descriptive survey research design was used. The population entails all the teaching staff and 2021/2022 Junior Secondary School students at public secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State. The study consists of 160 respondents (80 teachers & 80 students), this was arrived at by randomly selecting four public secondary schools using purposive sampling techniques. Educational Media and Academic Performance Questionnaire (EMAP) developed by researcher with reliability coefficient of 0.75 using the test-retest method. Descriptive and correlation statistical tools was used. Results revealed that 54(67.5%) agreed, 14(17.5%) strongly agreed that any lesson taught with educational media are remembered easily. Again, 42(52.5%) disagreed while 19(23.8%) strongly disagreed that the use of educational media prevents teacher's full class control. The highest mean value on student response was 3.51 while the highest standard deviation was 0.874. Results on teachers' response shows 42(52.5%) and 27 (33.8%) agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the use of educational media aids students' comprehension in learning. The highest mean value of teachers' responses 3.49, 3.48, 3.40, 3.27, and 3.24 was indicated in items 7,8,5,1, and10 respectively while the standard deviation ascendingly ranges from 0.935, 0.8n78, 0.876, 0.868 and 0.853 as revealed in item 2,3,9,4 and 6 respectively. It was concluded that governmental, non-governmental, and professional organizations should help the schools provide educational media and recommended that state secondary schools must all have educational media centers installed in the schools.

Keywords: Educational Media, Academic Performance, Computer Assisted Instruction & Students

Introduction

The availability of educational media significantly improved the academic performance of secondary school students. Educational media covers all the tools and tangible resources a teacher could employ to carry out a lesson plan and help pupils meet learning goals. Since instructors became the major method of delivering instruction to students in the 1900s, educational media have existed. According to Duban (2019), the first school museum was established in St. Louis in 1905. Museums had supplementary educational resources that might help teachers when instructing various subjects. The first collection of instructional movies was created in 1910 for use in classrooms. In 1913, Thomas Edison stated, "Books in schools will soon be obsolete. In due course, education for students will be visual. With the help of a movie, you can instruct students in every field of study. Also, Usman & Madudili (2020) affirmed that researchers at IBM began to use computers in the 1950s and the first CAI application to be utilized in public schools was created by the researchers, who also created the Computer Assisted Instruction (CAI) author language. The majority of computer usage in primary schools was for drills and practice or for teaching student's computer-related skills like typing. However, it took until the 1980s for computers to gain widespread use as a teaching tool and this made it imperative to teach virtually all the subjects with the aid of using educational media.

Njoroge (2019) defines educational media as both print and nonprint materials that are intended to influence students' access to knowledge during the educational process. Print, textbooks, magazines, newspapers, presentations, photos, workbooks, and electronic media are only a few examples of the materials used in educational media. The use of educational

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media in the teaching-learning process is crucial. The availability of textbooks, proper chalkboards, math and science kits, teaching guides, science guides, audio-visual aids, overhead projectors, and other educational materials are crucial (Bukoyo 2019) However, practically all the state's secondary schools lack several amenities. The textbook is the first educational medium, claims Kamba (2019). Numerous definitions of a textbook emphasize its value as a teaching tool. The foundation of every learning activity connected to a certain curriculum is the textbook. The significance of textbooks in educating pupils in developing nations is crucial.

Ritakumari (2019) ascertained that there are numerous benefits to educational media in terms of reproducibility, portability, and improved equity access. Additionally, as they aid students in higher knowledge acquisition, educational media support teachers in their ability to impart knowledge in an impressive manner, improving the effectiveness of learning. Educational media is one of the factors that affect learning, therefore students who have access to information will study more ardently and be motivated (Puspitanni, & Hanif 2019) All the tools and physical equipment a teacher could employ to carry out a lesson plan and assist pupils in meeting their academic goals are referred to as educational media. In addition to more modern tools and materials like computers, DVDs, CD-ROMs, the internet, and interactive video conferencing, this may also include conventional tools e.g. charts, slides, overheads, real objects, etc. Diverse definitions exist for the phrase "educational media." In some circumstances, it alludes to the tools that instructors and students both employ. Other times, it solely refers to tools and resources utilized in the teaching and learning processes, such as printed materials or devices. According to Chand, Chaudhary Prasad & Chand (2021) educational media is a system component that may be used in the educational process and is used to distribute educational messages and ideas or to enable communication throughout the teaching and learning process.

The term "educational media" describes forms of media that disseminate information for educational purposes. Without functional educational media to support inventive output in contemporary disciplines like science and technology, among others, effective instruction could not be possible. Idris (2018) claimed that regardless of a child's moral, mental, emotional, or psychological state of health, education is the key to a nation's true growth and progress. In the Universal Basic Education curriculum teachers are also expected to use a variety of high-quality educational media for effective and efficient teaching and learning activities in the classroom. Ritakumari (2019) listed a few factors that teachers should take into account before choosing educational media.

Firstly, the learner's age and abilities should be considering, the teacher must be very careful to take the kids' ages and skills into consideration. The purpose of educational media is to enhance learning and not to hamper it in any way, therefore, the process and procedure for selection should be germane and effective for successful outcome. Secondly, Educational media must be relevant to the lesson objectives; one of the major stages of teaching and learning is stating of educational objectives which will later determine the outcome of that lesson at the evaluation stage, to ascertain the attainment of the lesson objectives, there is need to ensure that the selected educational media is relevant to the lesson. Thirdly, informational currency: Any instructional media that is appropriate for use in the classroom must be up to date. Despite the desire for technological advancement, secondary school topics are crucial to it, and as a result, their teaching and learning, as well as students' subpar academic performance, have become a sort of source of concern for all parties involved. Ritakumari (2019) asserts that the following aspects of educational media are relevant:

1. The foundation of the educational system is the teacher. High-quality teaching and learning processes are maintained with the support of qualified teachers. The high results are then impacted by this. Leaders provide an example of how to execute the curriculum both within and outside of the classroom. The manner that which technology is used and integrated into the teaching and learning process is significantly impacted by its deployment.
2. Different educational media and multimedia technologies are currently used in teaching and learning processes. These include computer systems, microphones, mobile devices, interactive whiteboards, digital-video-on-demand, online media streams, digital games, podcasts, and more.
3. Educational media support the teaching and learning process from the lesson's introduction to its evaluation, or from beginning to end. It offers tangible experiences that act as a foundation for thinking, arguing, and problem-solving. It improves both initial learning and learning retention.
4. The modern educational system is heavily reliant on computers. Internet research is more convenient for students than browsing through thick books. Learning now extends beyond textbooks to the internet, where there is a wealth of knowledge.
5. Education now extends well beyond the four walls of the classroom. Due to computers and the internet, locations that were once far apart have become closer. Information presentation has gotten simpler; this has made audio-visual representation of information easier and made teaching and learning more engaging.

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6. A computer system enables a teacher to showcase a new lesson, animate, present new materials, demonstrate how to use new applications, and display new websites in the classroom. Microphones can be employed in the teaching and learning process in a noisy classroom.
7. Mobile devices such as clickers or smartphones can be utilised in enhancing feedback activities during and after instruction delivery by the teacher. An interactive whiteboard provides touch control of computer applications which enhance the experience in the by displaying visuals that can be viewed on a wider screen by learners. This assist in visual learning, and interactivity for learners to draw, write or manipulate images on the interactive whiteboard.
8. With digital video, there is no longer a need for hardware players in the classroom, and both instructors and students can instantly view video content without a connection to the internet. Online media streams can improve classroom teaching and learning procedures on websites that stream video. The use of the digital game, which encourages students to learn the topic at hand, is growing daily. Podcasts are a relatively innovation and are a popular medium for accessing and consuming audio and video content. Computer and telecommunications system integration is known as video conferencing.

The use of educational media in teaching and learning is necessary for effective and high-quality instruction. In Nigeria and all other African nations, secondary schools' education must properly guide in order to improve academic achievement. Therefore this, study assessed the Educational Media on Academic Performance among secondary school students in Oyo East Local Government Area of Oyo state.

Objectives of the study:

1. To examine the student's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?
2. To determine the teacher's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?
3. To find the significant relationship between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.
4. To elicits the different between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Research Questions:

1. What is the student's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?
2. What are the teacher's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?

Research Hypothesis

1. There is no significant relationship between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.
2. There is significant different between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Methodology

The study adopted descriptive research design. The population entails all the teaching staff and 2021/2022 Junior Secondary School students at public secondary schools in Oyo East Local Government, Oyo State. The study consists of 160 respondents (80 teachers & 80 students), this was arrived at by randomly selecting four public secondary schools in Oyo East local government using purposive sampling techniques. Educational Media and Academic Performance Questionnaire (EMAPQ) developed by researcher with reliability coefficient of 0.75 using the test-retest method. The researchers visited the chosen school twice, the first time was to see the principal for the briefing on the research study and to seek for permission for the use of the school. After the proper documentation and the appropriate approval, all the 80 students and 80 teachers randomly chosen in the four schools were asked to respond to the questions on the instrument that was made available to them for the study. They received guarantees that all the information would be kept completely private and used only for study. All the instruments were properly filled and returned on the spot. This research used descriptive statistical method such as frequency and percentage to examine the influence of instructional media on academic performances of secondary school students of public schools. Also, the correlation was conducted to establish the relationship between the teacher's response and the student's response.

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Results

Research Question 1

What are the student's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?

Table 1: Students Response

S/N	ITEMS	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagreed	Strongly Disagreed	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	I noticed improvement in my academic performance especially subject taught with Educational Media	21 (26.3)	43 (57.%)	10 (12.5%)	06 (7.5%)	3.44	.624
2	I easily remembered any lesson taught with the aid of Educational Media	14 (17.5)	54 (67.%)	07 (8.8%)	05 (6.3%)	3.24	.784
3	I hardly understand some subjects without the aid of Educational Media	18 (22.5)	33 (41.%)	21 (26.3%)	08 (10%)	2.78	.874
4	There is no difference in my academic performance with the use of Educational Media	29 (36.3)	33 (41.%)	14 (17.5%)	04 (5%)	3.25	.702
5	Educational Media affected my performance poorly because it confuses me	11 (13.8)	24 (30%)	39 (48.8%)	06 (7.5%)	2.56	.842
6	The use of educational media helps my retentive ability	19 (23.8)	49 (61.%)	07 (8.8%)	05 (6.3%)	3.37	.594
7	The use of educational media catches my attention in the class.	12 (15%)	44 (55%)	13 (16.3%)	11 (13.8%)	3.17	.687
8	My academic performance improves whenever the use of educational media was adopted	29 (36.3)	41 (51.%)	03 (3.8%)	07 (8.8%)	3.51	.524
9	The use of educational media do not allows the teacher to have full class control.	11 (13.8)	08 (10%)	42 (52.5%)	19 (23.8%)	2.20	.858
10	I always prefer educational media teaching to a non-educational media teaching	27 (33.8)	42 (52.%)	08 (10%)	03 (3.8%)	3.24	.783

Sources: Data Collection by Researcher

This table shows the student's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Research Question 2

What are the teacher's responses to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance?

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Table 2: Teachers Response

S/N	ITEMS	Strongly Agreed	Agreed	Disagree	Strongly Disagree	Mean	Standard Deviation
1	My students' performance has improved since we started using Media	17 (21.3)	46 (57.%)	07 (8.8%)	10 (12.5%)	3.27	.702
2	Educational media is only good to teach some selected topics	12 (15%)	16 (20%)	38 (47.5%)	14 (17.5%)	2.15	.935
3	The students' performance in competitions with other schools has improved since Educational Medias is in place	18 (22.5)	43 (53.%)	11 (13.8%)	08 (10.%)	2.64	.878
4	There is no difference in performance of the student with or without Educational Media	09 (11.3%)	13 (16.%)	38 (47.5%)	20 (25%)	2.20	.868
5	Educational media is a tool for effective teaching and learning process	21 (26.3)	43 (53.%)	11 (13.8%)	05 (6.3%)	3.40	.635
6	I do not enjoy teaching without educational media	11 (13.8)	13 (16.%)	32 (40%)	24 (30%)	2.40	.853
7	Special training is required in using educational media to teach	18 (22.5)	44 (55%)	10 (12.5%)	08 (10%)	3.49	.586
8	The use of educational media aid students' comprehension in learning	27 (33.8)	42 (52.%)	05 (6.3%)	06 (7.5%)	3.48	.566
9	Educational media are difficult to handle for teaching and learning process	14 (17.5)	28 (35%)	25 (31.3%)	13 (16.3%)	2.78	.876
10	The use of educational media for teaching and learning is time consuming	23 (28.8)	40 (50%)	07 (8.8%)	10 (12.5%)	3.24	.784

Sources: Data Collection by Researcher

Table 2 shows the teacher's response to the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Hypothesis 1

There is no significant relationship between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Table 3: This table shows the result of the correlation between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

	N	Total Mean	Average Mean	Total Standard Deviation	Average Standard Deviation
Students Response	80	30.76	3.08	7.272	0.73
Teachers Response	80	29.05	2.91	6.981	0.70

Table 3 shows the value of students' and teachers' responses in terms of mean and standard deviation, the total mean of the student's response and teachers' response totaling 30.76 (3.08) and 29.05 (2.91) respectively while the standard deviation revealed a total of 7.272 (0.73) and 6.981 (0.70). it was noticed from the results that both students and teachers have similar opinions on the influence of educational media on students' academic performance since the mean and standard deviation have a close range of differences.

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Hypothesis 2

There is significant different between the response of the students and the teachers on the assessment of educational media on Academic Performance.

Table 3 Correlations

		Sum (Students)	Sum (Teachers)
Sum (Students)	Pearson Correlation	1	0.191
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.183
	N	79	80
Sum (Teachers)	Pearson Correlation	0.191	0
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.183	
	N	80	80

There is strong positive relationship between the student response and teachers' response and is statistically significant $r(80) = 0.18, p = 0.19$. Hence, the correlation between the students' response and that of their teachers is significant. Therefore, Null Hypothesis two (H_{02}) was rejected.

Table 4: t-Test: Paired Two Sample for Means

	Students	Teachers
Mean	3.08	2.91
Variance	4.564898	4.473877551
Observation	80	80
Pearson Correlation	0.191294	
Hypothesized Mean Difference	0	
Df	79	
t Stat	1.516912	
P (T<=t) one tail	0.067857	
T Critical one tail	1.676551	
P (T<=t) one tail	0.135715	
t Critical two-tail	2.009575	

The p -value is 0.135715 greater than 0.05 alpha level, we reject the H_{02} . Hence, there is no significant different between the students and the teachers' responses.

Discussion of Findings

Table 1a revealed the student's opinions on the four likert scale namely Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly Disagree (SD) in respect to each of the statements in the influence of educational media on the secondary school students' academic performance in Oyo east local government area of oy state. The table indicated their perspectives in frequency and percentage shown in the bracket. Moreover, mean value and the standard deviation for each of the statements was also calculated and presented. The student's opinion about 8 out of the 10 items has the highest rating value as majority of them either strongly agreed or agreed. 54 (67.5%) agreed and 14 (17.5%) out of 80 respondents strongly agreed that they easily remembered any lesson taught with educational media. Also 49 (61.3%) accepted to agree while 19 (23.8%) strongly agreed that the use of educational media helps their retentive ability. Moreover, 41 (51.3%) respondents, 29 (36.3%) believed their academic performance improves whenever the use of educational media was adopted. On the contrary, a few numbers of respondents also either strongly disagreed or disagreed with certain statement, for example 42 (52.5%) totally disagreed while 19 (23.8%) joined to strongly disagreed that the use of educational media do not allow teachers to have full class control during teaching and learning process. In addition, 39 (48.8%) disagreed and 6 (7.5%) strongly disagreed that educational media affected their performance poorly because it causes confusion in learning. The highest mean value was 3.51 on item 8 which stated that academic performance improves when educational media is used while the highest standard deviation value was 0.874 on item 3 that they hardly understand some subjects without the use of educational media.

This table 1b presented the Teacher's opinion in respect to each of the statements in the influence of educational media in the secondary school students' academic performance in Oyo East local government area. The table shows their perspectives both in frequency and percentage in bracket under the heading Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D), and Strongly

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Disagree (SD). It also shows the mean value and the standard deviation (SD) for each of the statements. The highest value of 46 (57.5%) where the teachers agreed that students' academic performance improved since they started using educational media in teaching. Another statement of interest was found in no 8, the results shows that 42 (52.5%) and 27 (33.8%) were agreed and strongly agreed respectively that the use of educational media aid students' comprehension in learning. Furthermore, 44 (55%) agreed and 18 (22.5%) strongly agreed that special training is required in using educational media to teach. 40 (50%) and 23 (28.8%) respondents both agreed and strongly agreed respectively in their responses that the use of educational media for teaching and learning is time consuming. Although, a total of 56 (70%) were either disagreed or strongly disagreed that they do not enjoy teaching without educational media as stated on item 6, this revealed that they still enjoy teaching with or without educational media. Another statement in this dimension was stated in item 2 that educational media is only good to teach some selected topics, no fewer than 52 (67.5%) either disagreed or strongly disagreed, they believed that there is no topic that cannot be taught with educational media. The highest mean value of 3.49, 3.48, 3.40, 3.27 and 3.24 was indicated in item 7,8,5,1, and10 respectively while the standard deviation ascendingly ranges from 0.935, 0.878, 0.876, 0.868 and 0.853 as revealed in item 2,3,9,4 and 6 respectively.

Table 2 shows the value of students' and teachers' responses in terms of mean and standard deviation, the total mean of the student's response and teachers' response totaling 30.76 (3.08) and 29.05 (2.91) respectively while the standard deviation revealed a total of 7.272 (0.73) and 6.981 (0.70). it was noticed from the results that both students and teachers have similar opinions on the influence of educational media on students' academic performance since the mean and standard deviation have a close range of differences.

Conclusion

The secondary level of education is crucial because it serves as both a transitional period between primary and university education and the foundation of the labor force in the nation. In order to achieve the intended objectives, it is required to create a body that will be in charge of its efficient implementation process. Any less will result in the secondary education system consistently producing mediocre work that will exacerbate Nigeria's economic, social, and political issues. The conclusion that can be drawn from the examination of the data is that the use of educational media can improve the teaching and learning process. The use of print and electronic media in the classroom will improve secondary school pupils' academic performance. Given this, governmental, non-governmental, and professional organizations should help the schools provide educational media. In the event that the necessary materials are not accessible, teachers occasionally have to improvise.

Recommendations

1. As educational media are generally helpful to students' academic progress, secondary school teachers are rapidly becoming more aware of their use. It is crucial that the proper arrangements be established for its provision and utilization as a result.
2. Governments or management organizations should make a greater effort to supply schools with crucial instructional material and to hire qualified professionals who can make the most use of it.
3. The government should also regularly organize workshops and training sessions on how to use educational media in teaching and learning.
4. The state's secondary schools must all have educational media centers installed; this will inspire both students and teachers to enhance the teaching and learning process.
5. Good academic performance as a result of the use of educational media should be praised, and teachers should be encouraged to use it to educate in the classroom.
6. Teachers or subject-matter experts should instruct students on the creation and improvisation of instructional media.
7. The maintenance and storage of educational media should be handled appropriately.

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